



2 A213S, 1 L213M, 1 L213T, 1 M213A, 1 M213I, 1 M213L, 2 M213S, 2 M213T, 1 S213M, 3 S213T, 3 T213A, 1 T213I, 3 T213L



- M
- I
- T
- L
- {LT}
- A
- S

- Bathybatini
- Benthochromini
- Boulengerochromini
- Cyphotilapiini
- Cyprichromini
- Ectodini
- Eretmodini
- Gobiocichlini
- Haplochromini
- Heterotilapini
- Lamprologini
- Limnochromini
- Perissodini
- Serranochromini
- Steatocranini
- Tilapiini
- Trematocarini
- Tropheini

0 2 4 6 8 10 12

2 A213S, 1 L213M, 1 L213T, 1 M213A, 1 M213I, 1 M213L, 2 M213S, 2 M213T, 1 S213M, 3 S213T, 3 T213A, 1 T213I, 3 T213L



- M
- I
- T
- L
- {LT}
- A
- S

- shallow
- intermediate
- deep
- NA

0 2 4 6 8 10 12

2 A213S, 1 L213M, 1 L213T, 1 M213A, 1 M213I, 1 M213L, 2 M213S, 2 M213T, 1 S213M, 3 S213T, 3 T213A, 1 T213I, 3 T213L



0 2 4 6 8 10 12